

Dye-surfactant interactions in mixed aqueous-organic solvent media with different hydrophobicity

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Manuscript received online 05 February 2013, accepted 19 April 2013

Abstract : The interaction of pinacyanol chloride (PC) dye and an anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl benzene sulpho-nate (SDBS) in mixed aqueous-organic solvent media with different hydrophobic character has been studied spectropho-tometrically. The organic solvents chosen for the study are ethylene glycol, 2-methoxy ethanol, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, ethylamine, diethylamine, triethylamine, monoethanolamine, diethanolamine, triethanolamine and polyethylene glycols. Presence of sharp isobestic point at around 555 nm in the absorption spectra of PC-SDBS in the mixed media except those containing PEG indicated that there is strong interaction between the dye and the surfactant leading to formation of 1 : 1 dye-surfactant complex. The binding constant, K_c of the dye with the surfactant in mixed aqueous-organic media containing 5% organic solvent by volume has been evaluated using Scott's equation. There is generally an increase in K_c in presence of the organic solvent except for the 2-methoxy ethanol or tetrahydrofuran. In the mixed media containing an amine, a sharp increase in K_c was observed with the introduction of more hydrophobic ethyl groups in the amine while for mixed media containing an alcohol amine, presence of less hydrophobic (i.e. more hydrophilic) $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ groups led to decreasing K_c . The results clearly indicate that increase in the hydrophobic character besides the solvent polarity of the mixed media favors the formation of the dye-surfactant complex.

Keywords : Pinacyanol chloride, SDBS, dye-surfactant interaction, mixed media, binding constant, solvent hydrophobicity.

Introduction

Investigations on different aspects of dye-surfactant interactions continues to be intensely researched in view of its importance and contemporary relevance with po-tential for industrial applications particularly in textile industry¹⁻³. The interaction of a dye with surfactant brings about a drastic change in the spectral behavior of the dye which renders spectrophotometric technique a versatile tool in the study of dye-surfactant interactions⁴⁻¹⁰. Of the various factors that influence the dye-surfactant interac-tions, the increase in the hydrophobic tail of the surfac-tant and more importantly, changes in the hydrophobic character of the dye molecule play an important role in determining the extent of interaction between the dye and surfactant molecules^{11,12}. Besides, any change in the po-larity or the hydrophobicity of the solvent media in which the dye is dissolved is known to affect the aggregation behavior of the dye as well as the surfactant, which in turn would bring about perturbation in the dye-surfactant

interaction¹³⁻¹⁵. Most of investigations on dye-surfactant interactions have so far been carried out in aqueous me-dia excepting a few in alcohol or dimethylformamide mixed aqueous media¹⁶⁻¹⁹. In spite of extensive studies on the dye surfactant interaction, there is hardly any attempt to study how changes in the hydrophobic character of the solvent media would affect the dye surfactant interaction. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the dye-surfactant interaction in different mixed aqueous organic media having different hydrophobic character. In this paper, we report the finding of the spectrophotometric study on the interaction of pinacyanol chloride, PC and an anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl benzene sulpho-nate, SDBS in aqueous and mixed aqueous-organic sol-vent media. The organic solvents chosen for the study are ethylene glycol (EG), 2-methoxy ethanol (ME), diox-ane (DIO), tetrahydrofuran (THF), ethylamine (EAM), diethylamine (DAM), triethylamine (TAM), monoethanolamine (MEA), diethanolamine (DEA) and

triethanolamine (TEA) and polyethylene glycol series (PEG-200, PEG-300, PEG-400, PEG-600).

Materials and method :

The sample of the dye pinacyanol chloride (PC) and the anionic surfactant, SDBS were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (USA) and were used as received. The samples of PEG-200, PEG-300, PEG-400 and PEG-600 procured from CDH (India) were used as received. All the organic solvents of AR grade employed in the study, namely, EG, ME, MEA, DEA, TEA and THF were procured from Merck (India), EAM, TAM and DIO from Glaxo India Ltd. and DAM from SRL, India were purified following standard procedures and fractionally distilled prior to their use²⁰.

The absorption spectra of the dye solutions were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-2450 UV-Visible spectrophotometer using a pair of quartz cuvette of 1 cm optical length kept in a cell holder around which thermostated water from a Haake DC-10 was circulated. All the measurements were carried out at 303.15 ± 0.1 K.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of the PC in aqueous solution is characterized by two major peaks, one centered around 600 and the other around 550 nm along with a weak shoulder at around 520 nm. The first two bands have been assigned to the monomer and dimer species of the dye respectively and the weak shoulder to other higher aggregates^{7,21}. The absorption spectra of PC dye (10.0 μ M) in presence of different concentration of SDBS (0.1–4 mM) in pure aqueous media is shown in the Fig. 1. As has been reported earlier, presence of the anionic surfactant, SDBS perturbs the spectral behavior of the PC dye due to the dye-surfactant interactions⁵. At low concentration of SDBS (much below its CMC) there is significant decrease with small red shift in both the monomer and the dimer bands along with the appearance of a new band at around 490 nm, which has been attributed to formation of dye-surfactant complex^{4,5}. But beyond the CMC of the surfactant (0.96 mM), the intensity of the new band decreases along with a bathochromic shift except in mixed solvent containing an amine which showed hypsochromic

Fig. 1. Visible absorption spectra of 10.0 μ M PC dye (dotted line) in presence of different amounts of SDBS (0.2 to 4 mM).

shift with gradual increase in the intensity of the monomer and the dimer band. The increase in the monomer band intensity, however, is much more rapid as compared to the dimer band. This has been attributed to the preferential interactions of the dye with the surfactant monomers while in presence of SDBS micelles the dye-aggregates would de-aggregate leading to sharp increase of the monomer band^{22–24}. The shift in the band position of the dye-surfactant complex has been plotted as a function of the surfactant concentration in Fig. 2. The CMC of the surfactant may be determined from the sharp change observed in such plots^{5,14,25}. The value of the CMC thus obtained has been included in Table 1. It may be of pertinence to mention here that no significant change in the spectral behavior of the dye was observed in presence of a cationic, CTAB (1.5 mM) or a non ionic, Triton X-100 (0.6 mM) surfactant which indicated that there are no

Fig. 2. Shift in the 1 : 1 dye-surfactant complex band, λ_{\max} with the surfactant concentration.

Table 1. Values of K_c of PC-SDBS in aqueous and mixed aqueous-organic solvent media containing 5% organic solvent by volume along with the CMC of SDBS in the mixed media

Organic solvent (5%)	λ_{\max} (nm)	CMC ^a (mM)	$K_c \times 10^{-3}$ (M ⁻¹)
Water	489	0.96	1.50
EG	478	0.78	1.67
ME	480	0.81	1.27
DIO	474	0.89	2.94
THF	461	0.79	1.07
EAM	482	–	1.52
DAM	480	–	8.65
TAM	470	–	8.86
MEA	485	0.75	7.03
DEA	482	0.82	4.87
TEA	480	0.91	1.95

λ_{\max} – wavelength of the maximal absorption peak of the PC-SDBS complex.

^aCMC could not be determined precisely in mixed media containing an amine since they showed hypsochromic rather than bathochromic shift.

appreciable interactions of PC with CTAB or TX-100 at least in the concentration range employed.

In a recent paper on the tendency of a dye or a surfactant to self aggregate in mixed aqueous organic solvent media, we have shown that changes in the hydrophobicity of the organic solvent is more dominating factor than changes in the solvent polarity or the dielectric effects^{21,26}. While the dye aggregates are preferably formed, formation of the surfactant micelles is delayed in presence of organic solvent with more hydrophobic groups in the mixed media. In view of the interesting behavior of the dye or the surfactant in mixed media, we have studied the PC dye-SDBS interaction in mixed aqueous organic solvent containing 5% by volume of the organic solvent with a view to highlighting the role of the solvent hydrophobicity on the dye surfactant interactions.

Representative spectra of the PC-SDBS system in mixed aqueous organic solvent containing 5% EG are shown in Fig. 3. The spectra is more or less similar with those in pure aqueous media except for the blue shift of the complex band from 490 to about 478 nm with sharper increase of the monomer band at higher surfactant concentration. Similar behaviors were observed in all the mixed

Fig. 3. Representative spectra of 10.0 μ M PC dye in mixed media containing 5% EG by volume (dotted line) in presence of different amounts of SDBS (0.2 to 3 mM).

aqueous organic solvent media under study except in presence of PEG series, which exhibited a different pattern as shown in Fig. 4. In mixed media containing PEG, there is no appreciable increase in the intensities of either the monomer or dimer bands with increase in the surfactant

Fig. 4. Visible absorption spectra of 10.0 μ M PC dye in mixed media containing 5% PEG-200 by volume (dotted line) in presence of different amounts of SDBS (0.12 to 2.2 mM).

concentration. This perhaps is an indication that SDBS preferentially interacts with PEG while the dye molecules mostly remain as aggregates in presence of PEG giving rise to such complicated spectra with no clear isobestic point. The spectra of PC-SDBS system in all the mixed media under study except those containing PEG are conspicuous by the presence of a sharp isobestic point at around 555 nm confirming the presence of 1 : 1 complex in the system.

The binding constant, K_c of the 1 : 1 complex may be computed using Scott eq. (1)^{27,28} :

$$[D_0].[S_0]/(d - d_0) = [S_0]/(\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0) + 1/K_c (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0) \quad (1)$$

where, D_0 is the initial molar concentration of dye and S_0 the initial molar concentration of surfactant, d and d_0 the absorbance of dye at the absorption maximum of the complex with and without surfactant respectively and ϵ_c and ϵ_0 are the molar extinction co-efficient of the complex and the dye at the absorption maximum of the complex.

The linear plots of $[D_0].[S_0]/(d-d_0)$ against $[S_0]$ for the dye-surfactant systems in all the mixed media except those containing PEG as shown in the Fig. 5 confirms formation of 1 : 1 complex in all the systems. The value of the binding constant, K_c for the complex in different mixed media was then computed from the slope and the intercept of such linear plots. The values of K_c thus obtained in the mixed aqueous organic media along with the CMC are presented in the Table 1.

phobic (alkyl) groups in organic solvent would increase the CMC of the surfactant by delaying micellization while the dye aggregates would be preferentially formed^{21,26}.

It is observed from Table 1 that presence of the organic solvent except ME or THF resulted into an increase in K_c . Maximum K_c was found in mixed media containing triethylamine (TAM) while it showed a minimum in presence of THF. Being relatively more hydrophobic than the other organic solvents under study, TAM would stabilize the monomers of the surfactant, which would favor enhanced interaction with the dye by de-aggregating the dyes-aggregates present in TAM mixed media. The lower CMC of SDBS in THF mixed media implies that presence of THF favors the formation of SDBS micelles while facilitating the formation of dye aggregates at the same time²¹. This would considerably weaken the dye-surfactant interactions and hence the sharp

Fig. 5. Plot of $[D_0][S_0]/(d - d_0)$ vs $[S_0]$ for PC-SDBS system in aqueous and mixed aqueous organic solvent media.

Micellization of SDBS occurs at much lower concentration in presence of the dye, which has been ascribed to early micellization induced by the dye. For the mixed media containing amines, CMC of the surfactant could not be determined precisely since they showed hypsochromic rather than bathochromic shift of the complex band unlike the others. Presence of the organic solvent in general lowers the polarity of the medium, which would reduce the tendency of the dye molecule to self-aggregate but induce early micellization of the surfactant thereby lowering the CMC²⁹. However, increasing the hydrophobic character of the mixed media with more hydro-

phobic character of the mixed media containing THF or ME. However, besides the hydrophobicity of the mixed media, organic solvent-water, organic solvent-surfactant and organic solvent-dye interactions are expected to influence the formation of the dye-surfactant complex.

The value of K_c in EAM was found to be $1.52 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ whereas in mixed solvent containing MEA, it is found to be $7.03 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$. The relatively large increase in K_c in presence of MEA as compare to that of EAM may be due to decreased hydrophobic character of the mixed media due to presence of $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ group in MEA. Earlier in our paper, we have reported that the PC dye mono-

mers are favored in presence of alcoholamines. Therefore, presence of the alcoholamines would favor stronger interaction with the anionic surfactant and hence a sharp increase in the K_C value in MEA mixed media. However, K_C in presence of DEA or TEA was observed to be less than those of DAM or TAM respectively. Though the introduction of more $-CH_2CH_2OH$ groups in the alcoholamine further stabilizes the dye monomers, it would also facilitate early micellization of SDBS thereby weakening the dye-surfactant interaction. In the mixed media containing an amine, introduction of more ethyl (hydrophobic) groups in the amine led to increasing K_C in the order : EAM < DAM < TAM. The results therefore clearly indicate that increasing the hydrophobic character of the mixed media favors the formation of the dye-surfactant complex. This is further corroborated by the observation that K_C in mixed media containing DIO is larger than that of THF which may be attributed to the larger hydrophobic surface area coupled with the fluxional nature of the dioxane molecule.

Conclusion

The interaction of PC dye with an anionic surfactant SDBS leading to formation of 1 : 1 dye-surfactant complex has been studied in aqueous and mixed aqueous organic solvent media. The organic solvent chosen for the study include ethylene glycol, 2-methoxy ethanol, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, ethylamine, diethylamine, triethylamine, monoethanolamine, diethanolamine, triethanolamine and polyethylene glycol. The binding constant of the dye with the surfactant in all the mixed media except for solvent containing PEG has been evaluated. The binding constant was found to increase in all mixed media except the ones containing ME or THF. In the mixed media containing an amine, a sharp increase in K_C was observed with the introduction of more hydrophobic ethyl groups in the amine and maximum K_C was observed in mixed media containing triethylamine. But in alcohol amine, presence of less hydrophobic (i.e. more hydrophilic) $-CH_2CH_2OH$ groups led to decreasing K_C . The results clearly indicate that increase in the hydrophobic character of the mixed media besides the solvent polarity favored the dye-surfactant interaction.

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